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Instruct-ULTRA

Integrating Structural Biology

Instruct-ULTRA

WP5 - Reaching new user communities and industry

Lead Beneficiary: P1-Instruct

Leader: Lucia Banci (P12-CIRMMP)

Deliverable: 5.5 Outreach programme for new academic communities including an information pack.

Contractual delivery date: 31 Aug 2018

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Project objective

To set up appropriate service provision tools open to new communities.

D5.5 relates to task 5.3 of WP5 on attracting new academic communities to the services of Instruct-ERIC.

Executive summary

A plan has been developed to promote Instruct-ERIC services to non-structural biologists in the life sciences. During 2018, scientific sessions were hosted at the Federation of European Neuroscience Societies (FENS) Forum and the Federation of European Biochemistry Societies (FEBS) Congress, as a pilot study for future activities. A literature review highlighted particular life science fields where structural biology techniques have particular relevance but are currently underexploited. These fields will be targeted for promotional activities. Following the success of the FENS and FEBS events, and learning from these experiences, a conference schedule has been created for 2019, and potential partnering research infrastructures have been identified. The use of targeted social media, sponsorship opportunities and open calls for research proposals are considered. The Instruct-ERIC website has been significantly tailored to attract and meet the needs of life scientists without a background in structural biology, and an online

information pack has been developed for Instruct-ERIC members to use to promote services to new communities.

1. Introduction

Proposals for access to the services technologies of Instruct-ERIC come from three academic communities:

- (i) structural biologists, requiring access to specialist or unique instrumentation in their respective fields, e.g. an NMR spectroscopist requiring access to 950 MHz NMR instrument not available locally.
- (ii) structural biologists that require access to infrastructures different from their major field of expertise e.g., crystallographic groups using NMR facilities and/or cryo-EM.
- (iii) non-structural biologists from fields such as biochemistry, immunology, virology, without prior experience in structural biology, interested in structural information.

Currently access data show that this group (iii) collectively represents approximately 10% of Instruct proposals requesting access. Therefore, the overall aim of this task is to increase the user base from the non-structural biologists and hence broaden the scientific impact of Instruct-ERIC. This deliverable describes the development of an outreach programme and associated tools for attracting new academic communities to Instruct-ERIC.

2. Promotion within Structural Biology Communities

The services and technologies of Instruct-ERIC are relatively well promoted within structural biology communities. As an indication, more than 500 scientific talks were given by Instruct-ULTRA partner scientists, referencing Instruct-ERIC, during January 2017-June 2018. Some of this activity has involved audiences from other disciplines and therefore contributes to increasing the visibility of Instruct-ERIC. Instruct-ULTRA is actively supporting this by providing partners with a summary slide for inclusion in presentations (ref. D1.4) (see section 11).

3. Pilot promotional activities in the first reporting period Jan 17 – Jul 18

In the first reporting period it was decided to pilot promotional activities at two academic conferences, so that new approaches could be tested out, with a view to creating a template that could be replicated at future events. With neuroscience highlighted in the Instruct-ULTRA technical annex as a key area for Instruct-ERIC to gain access, the Federation of European Neuroscience Societies (FENS) conference in July 2018 was selected as one of the conferences to target. Building on previous links that Instruct had established with the Federation of European Biochemical Societies (FEBS), the annual FEBS meeting that attracts a broad audience in molecular sciences, was selected for the second event.

Instruct-ULTRA led an initiative to partner with EU Openscreen and EuroBioImaging to sponsor a Networking Session at the FENS meeting in July 2018. Prof Radu Aricescu (LMB, Cambridge, UK) gave an excellent scientific talk, describing how Instruct services allowed him to solve the

protein structure by cryo-EM of a multi-subunit membrane protein, the GABAA receptor complex. Naomi Gray gave a short introduction to Instruct-ERIC, alongside introductions from the other two research consortia. The event drew an audience of 60 people, representing industry and researchers from many European countries. Several participants remarked that they would be keen to make use of the services provided by Instruct-ERIC. This event was particularly fruitful in terms of networking and raising awareness of European Research Infrastructures.

Figure 1. Promotional slide of the Instruct-ERIC / EU Openscreen ERIC / EuroBioImaging joint session at FENS 2018.

For the Federation of European Biochemistry Societies (FEBS) congress a special session was organized, in collaboration with EU Openscreen to promote the use of research infrastructures in Europe. Dr Jan Dohnálek from the Instruct-CZ Centre, one of two speakers at the session described his work on zinc-dependent nucleases, and Naomi Gray (Instruct-ULTRA Project Manager) followed up with an introduction to Instruct-ERIC. The session at FEBS was an integral part of the programme, within the section “European Research Infrastructures”, and received very positive feedback from the session chair.

Figure 2. Promotional slide of the Instruct-ERIC / EU Openscreen ERIC joint session at FEBS 2018.

In terms of learning outcomes, it became clear that groundwork is needed to engage conference organisation committees prior to requesting a presence at meetings. In the cases of completely new communities e.g. FENS, Instruct-ERIC may need to be prepared to pay a fee to host a networking event and for hospitality costs. FEBS was an example of a society meeting where Instruct-ERIC already had a network of contacts. The society already had an understanding of European research infrastructures (RIs), with space on the programme assigned to feature such RIs. The initiative from Instruct-ULTRA was to form an alliance with other RIs to generate a bigger presence and to publicise more widely than possible with a single infrastructure. On the basis of the positive experience of the initial FENS session, efforts will be made to lobby the FENS forum, to host European Research Infrastructure sessions as part of their future scientific programmes, preferably without cost to Instruct (as for FEBS). It may take some time for such partnerships to develop, and seed money will continue to be needed as Instruct-ULTRA reaches into other completely new communities without prior links or contacts.

Whereas conference organisers have well developed opportunities for companies to exhibit or publicise their services by various forms of sponsorship or renting exhibition space, it seems that organisers in general have yet to gain awareness of ERICS and other European RIs. Since such infrastructures have a very different non-profit funding model, without large budgets for promotion, intentional relationship building and discussions about how societies and ERICs can partner together will be needed. The positive report from FEBS 2018, who warmly received Instruct-ERIC and partner infrastructures, can be used as leverage for future European societies and conferences, to request that similar sessions are arranged at other conferences.

Another lesson was the strength that comes from partnering with other research infrastructures. The collaborations with EU-Openscreen and EuroBioImaging resulted in a more substantive offering, to both conference organisers and participating researchers.

4. Which communities to target in the next reporting period for Instruct-ULTRA

In selecting communities to target, considerations include:

- Large amount of research already taking place (measure by pub med citations)
- Structural biology techniques have large potential but are yet to be fully exploited
- Addressing “Grand challenge” with global societal impact
- Communities with existing partners or networks with easier entry points
- Existing projects or networks or funding

As a way of exploring the impact of structural biology in different academic communities, a literature survey was carried covering the last two years, looking at the number of PubMed citations for a range of life science fields and specific structural biology techniques being used in those fields. Of particular interest were fields with high citation count, where there is large potential for structural biology techniques yet to be exploited (shown by low percentage of citations mentioning structural biology techniques). Results shown in Appendix 2 highlighted Pharmacology, Microbiology, Molecular Biology, Immunology and Virology.

After review of the literature and other considerations, it was decided to prioritise Pharmacology, Microbiology, Molecular Biology and Virology as new communities, and to continue to include Neuroscience in the focus along with the regular fields of Biochemistry and Biophysics. Bearing in mind that life science research is continually developing, the list of priority communities will be reviewed again in autumn 2019 to address novel and emerging areas of research.

5. Conference scheduling for 2019

In terms of which conferences to select, it was decided to choose either European conferences or international conferences taking place in Europe, since there will be a better representation from member countries and pipeline countries. Conferences that represent European Federations of national societies are usually well attended and should also have an agenda to promote European Research Infrastructures. Since there are limited resources, Instruct-ULTRA will prioritise large conferences, where the agenda includes structural biology. If there is already a speaker from an Instruct centre, that would be another reason to select the conference.

Refer to Appendix 2 for a list of potential conferences scheduled for 2019. From the large list, six conferences have been selected as being a priority for promoting Instruct-ERIC.

Conference	Field	Date and Location
ESV	Virology	28 Apr – 1 May 2019, Rotterdam
FEBS	Biochemistry	6-11 July 2019, Krakow
FEMS	Microbiology	7-11 July 2019, Glasgow
EBSA	Biophysics	20-24 July 2019, Madrid
EMBO / Basel Life	Molecular Biology	9-12 Sept 2019, Basel
ELRIG	Drug Discovery	5-6 Nov 2018, Liverpool

Table 1. Conferences for Instruct-ERIC to use for promotion during 2019

For information about the costs to present at conferences, please refer to Appendix 3 where a model template for planning purposes is given.

Of the conferences selected for 2019, FEBS will be a particular highlight for Instruct-ULTRA. The Instruct-ERIC deputy director Lucia Banci is leading one of the sessions, and the overall programme will be conducive to Structural Biology.

Since conferences are only announced approximately a year before the event, it is not possible to produce a detailed plan to cover the entire Instruct-ULTRA period. In order to remain flexible and continue to evaluate and adapt plans, it was decided to repeat the process to produce a conference schedule for 2020 in September 2019.

6. Conference Sponsorship and Exhibiting Opportunities

The sponsorship opportunities will be reviewed and considered for each of the conferences to be targeted in 2019, taking into account the sponsorship costs and priority of the meeting.

Exhibition costs vary greatly between conferences, for example renting a booth at an exhibition can cost between €900 and €7000.

Since FEBS 2019 will be a significant meeting for Instruct-ERIC, it has been decided to rent exhibition space, as a way to test the effectiveness of hosting a conference booth. Made possible by the reduced exhibition fees for 2019, this activity should allow Instruct-ERIC to become more prominent at the conference, with a natural meeting place for enquirers and easier distribution of brochures and information.

7. Partners for Promotion

As mentioned earlier, partnering with other research infrastructures gives extra weight to the message. For 2019, Instruct will seek to partner again with EU-Openscreen and EuroBioImaging, along with MIRRI (Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure) for FEMS. In addition, the RI-VIS project will be launched in early 2019, which aims to increase visibility of European Research Infrastructures. Project Manager Natalie Haley has already expressed interest in collaborating together to be present at key conferences, and sharing costs. RI-VIS will also be presenting at three international conferences, which Instruct-ULTRA will offer to support.

8. Use Social Media to specifically target new communities

Strategic use of social media can be used to develop awareness of Instruct-ERIC in new scientific communities. For example, at FENS, a tweet was released, giving information about Instruct-ERIC's scientific talk, citing #FENS2018, along with promotion of our catalogue and services. The tweet was picked up by the conference organisers, who retweeted, thereby advertising our services to their wide audience of neuroscientists (11,400 followers) and providing an endorsement.

FENS
@FENSorg

Tweets **7,853** Following **612** Followers **11.4K** Likes **8,022** Lists **94**

Fig 3. Tweet by FENS central account, which promoted Instruct-ERIC services.

Following this successful social media campaign, the techniques will be applied to all conferences where there is a presence in 2019.

Social media techniques will also be explored for key conferences in new scientific communities, where Instruct-ERIC does not have a specific presence. By smart use of hashtags for conferences timed for the peak time during the conference, information about Instruct-ERIC opportunities in the particular field can be effectively shared to conference attendees. This is known as Guerrilla or Ambush Marketing¹.

Following advice from another research infrastructure, during 2019 Instruct-ERIC will pilot publication on Linked In, of a technical report about the application of Structural Biology to a new community (to be determined).

More generally, the Instruct-ERIC twitter schedule will be adjusted to intentionally highlight research where structural biology was applied in neurology, pharmacology, immunology and virology. The aim is to generally build up awareness of structural biology in such fields.

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Guerrilla_marketing

9. Launch “Open Call” for research projects in a new field

Another innovative approach to target new communities is to launch an open call for research proposals in a particular field. To gain some extra publicity and to generate more interest in structural biology, one open call will be launched in 2019. The call will be tied in to one of the summer conferences where Instruct-ERIC has a strong presence, with the call launched at the conference and staying open for 3 months. The call will be advertised on the Instruct-ERIC website, and circulated by email, social media and through scientific societies. No extra investment will be needed to fund the call, since the research proposals will be processed by the usual Instruct-ERIC peer review route, and utilise access funding. (It will be explained in the call that only researchers from member countries are eligible for financial support). A full evaluation of the open call will be made afterwards, to determine if this model should be extended to other new fields.

10. Develop an information pack

The most important way to disseminate information for Instruct-ERIC will be online at the new Instruct-ERIC webpage. As much information as possible for new communities will be posted online. Two new webpages have already been produced with new communities in mind, “What is Structural Biology” <https://instruct-eric.eu/what-is-structural-biology> and “Information for Life Scientists” <https://instruct-eric.eu/information-for-life-scientists>, the latter which has a direct link from the home page.

An updated A5 brochure for Instruct-ERIC has been commissioned as part of Instruct-ULTRA, which is due to be completed in November 2018.

An online information pack has also been set up, whereby Instruct staff and partners will have easy access to a range of electronic promotional resources for use at meetings and conferences. Included in the pack are:

- Powerpoint slide to acknowledge Instruct-ERIC and Instruct-ULTRA
- Powerpoint presentation to introduce Instruct-ERIC
- Video clip to introduce Instruct-ERIC
- Instruct-ERIC national leaflet template, produced by Francesca Morelli P13, can be adapted for other countries.
- Exhibition poster
- Instruct-ERIC logo
- Instruct-ERIC member countries map

The resources are available on the Instruct-ERIC website, <https://instruct-eric.eu/content/welcome-to-instructs-press-office>

Dissemination Resources for Instruct Partners

- Instruct-ERIC dissemination single powerpoint slide for acknowledgements
- Introducing Instruct-ERIC video clip
- Introduction to Instruct-ERIC powerpoint
- Brief introduction to Instruct-ERIC and Instruct-ULTRA powerpoint
- Exhibition poster
- Instruct-ERIC logo
- Instruct-ERIC member countries map
- Instruct-ERIC member countries map with centres

15-Oct-2018 Meeting
5th CORBEL MIUF
Paris 🇫🇷

15-Oct-2018 Meeting
ELIXIR Innovation and SME Forum: Data Driven Innovation in Industrial Biotechnology
Frankfurt 🇩🇪

11 COUNTRIES	9 CENTRES	20 SITES	273 SERVICES	6875 USERS	373 PUBLICATIONS
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Fig 4. Screenshot of webpage excerpt where partners can access dissemination resources <https://instruct-eric.eu/content/welcome-to-instructs-press-office>

11. National Promotional Efforts

In the first reporting period, Instruct-ULTRA has supported Slovakia, Denmark and Portugal as they have hosted national structural biology conferences. Such conferences raise awareness of Structural Biology in general and also the opportunities which are available through Instruct-ERIC. Speakers from the UK have travelled to present, and finances have been invested. In 2019-2020 Instruct-ULTRA will widen such national efforts, and support other partners to host similar conferences to widen the reach of Instruct-ERIC into new European communities.

Appendix 1

As a way of exploring the impact of structural biology in different academic communities, a literature survey was carried covering the last two years, looking at the number of PubMed citations for a range of life science fields and specific structural biology techniques being used in those fields.

Field	Citations for field	Citations for field + "Cryo Electron Microscopy"	Citations for field + "X-ray crystallography"	Citations for field + "NMR spectroscopy"
Cancer	350000	116	1064	401
Pharmacology	318668	139	2530	616
Microbiology	125413	174	727	204
Immunology	108574	111	420	79
Biochemistry	102056	407	1821	758
Molecular biology	101547	605	2041	200
Neuroscience	81021	26	104	37
Endocrinology	34551	1	27	21
Virology	32533	82	164	18
Vaccine	29567	60	128	28
Antimicrobial resistance	19062	7	154	2
Alzheimer's	20285	18	69	45
Parkinson's	13975	10	21	17

Table 2. Pub Med citations for Life Science Research Fields and the use of structural biology techniques, Sept 16 – Sept 18

Figure 5. Graph of total PubMed citations for Life Science Research Fields, Sept 16-Sept 18

Figure 6. Chart showing percentage of pub med citations for life science fields mentioning NMR, CryoEM or X-ray crystallography Sept 16 – Sept 18.

The results indicate that the fields most commonly using structural biology are Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, which would be expected. The interesting finding was that several fields are using structural biology techniques (particularly X-ray crystallography), such as pharmacology, microbiology, virology, vaccine and antibiotic resistance. Given the large number of papers published in these fields, and the number of researchers employed in these areas, results suggest that structural biology is ripe for exploitation, and Instruct-ERIC would be well placed to introduce European researchers to these techniques and provide access.

Appendix 2: List of European societies representing new academic communities for Instruct-ERIC and conferences hosted for 2019 – 2020.

Life Science Field	European or International Association	website	2019 Conferences	Notes	Instruct-ERIC attendance?
Cancer	European Association for Cancer Research (EACR)	www.eacr.org		Next biennial is EACR Cancer Research Congress 17-20 June 2020	Attend 2020.
Pharmacology	Federation of European Pharmacological Societies (EPHAR)	www.epharm.org	EPHAR Congress 8 th European Congress of Pharmacology, 5-9 Jul 2019, Prague		
	European Association of Faculties of Pharmacy (EAFP)	www.efponline.eu	EAFP Annual Conference 2019, 15-17 May 2019, Krakow		
	ELRIG	https://elrig.org	Drug discovery, 5-6 Nov 2019, Liverpool		Attend 2019
Microbiology (also covers antimicrobial resistance)	Federation of European Microbiological Societies (FEMS)	www.fems-microbiology.eu	7-11 July 2019, Glasgow		Priority for 2019. Ask for a Research Infrastructure (RI) slot.
	Parasitology & Microbiology	https://parasitology.conferenceseries.com	6 th International Conference on Parasitology & Microbiology 29-30 July 2019, Amsterdam		
Antimicrobial resistance	Primarily covered within the Microbial Societies		World Anti-Microbial Resistance Congress, 26-27 Mar 2019, Berlin		
Biochemistry	Federation of European Biochemical Societies (FEBS)	www.febs.org	FEBS Congress 6-11 July 2019, Krakow		Priority to attend 2019. Ask for a Research Infrastructure (RI) slot like for 2018 congress.
Molecular biology	European Molecular Biology Organization (EMBO)	https://www.basellife.org	EMBO / Basel Life, 9-12 Sept 2019, Basel	Includes an industry dimension at Basel Life,.	Medium priority to attend 2019
Neuroscience	Federation of European Neuroscience Societies (FENS)	www.fens.org	FENS regional meeting 10-13 July 2019, Belgrade	Next biennial congress: FENS Congress 2020	Priority to attend for 2020. Ask for a RI slot.

Life Science Field	European or Internat'l Association	website	2019 Conferences	Notes	Instruct-ERIC attendance?
Neuroscience (cont.)	Neuroscience and Neurochemistry		28 th International Conference on Neuroscience and Neurochemistry, 13-14 June 2019, Barcelona	Not sure if well enough known	
	Neurology Congress		32 nd European Neurology Congress 22-24 July 2019, London		
Virology	European Society for Virology (ESV)	www.eusv.eu	European Congress of Virology (ECV) 28 Apr – 1 May 2019, Rotterdam www.ecv2019.com	Only every 3 years, so should try for 2019 if we want to	Attend 2019, ask for a RI slot. Try for a speaker from Finland.
Vaccine	International Society of Vaccines (ISV)	www.isv-online.org	ISV Annual congress should be in 2019		
	Vaccine Research and Development		Vaccine Research and Development 25-26 Mar 2019, Milan		
	Vaccines and Immunization		32 nd International Conference on Vaccines and Immunization, 21-22 Mar 2019		
	Euro Global Summit		36 th Euro Global Summit and Expo on Vaccines and Vaccination, 3-4 June 2019, London		
	Vaccines and Immunology		International congress on Vaccines and Immunology, 6-7 Dec 2018, Amsterdam		
Immunology	European Federation of Immunological Societies (EFIS)	www.efis.org	6 th European Congress of Immunology Belgrade 2021		Recommend attendance in 2021
	Molecular Immunology and Immunogenetics		Molecular Immunology and Immunogenetics, 4-5 March 2019, Barcelona		
	Immunobiology		Immunobiology Congress 2019 Oct 21-22 Rome		

Table 3. List of European societies representing new academic communities for Instruct-ERIC and conferences to be hosted for 2019 – 2020.

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Appendix 3: Cost to present at conferences:

The approximate costs to host a session at a European conference are as follows (figures are based on the costs from FEBS and FENS):

Item	Cost
Speaker flight and airport pickup	€300
Speaker hotel and subsistence (2 nights)	€200
Speaker registration for conference	Ideally should be free
Cost to host networking session and refreshments	0 - €600 (FEBS offered a Research Infrastructure slot free, but FENS charged for a networking event)
Instruct Project manager flight, hotel (1 night), subsistence	€360
Instruct PM registration	Ideally should be free
Total if fully paid by Instruct	€1660
Total if split between 2 partners	€910

Table 4. Costs for promoting Instruct-ERIC at a conference

Note: If share event with another ERIC or research infrastructure, then the first four costs listed in the table can be split between the organisations